

Nagara Charche: Literature Review Of How Bengaluru Communicates Public Health Issues

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Abstract

Bengaluru's rapid urbanization has intensified vulnerabilities to climate-related health risks, exemplified by recurring dengue outbreaks. This study examines how public health and climate communication flows across institutional and community levels in the city, with dengue serving as a case study. Using a qualitative approach, the research combines a PRISMA-based literature review (2020–2025) with desk analysis of government advisories, media reports, and citizen initiatives. A stakeholder map was developed to trace formal and informal communication pathways across Union, State, City, and municipal actors, as well as resident welfare associations, NGOs, and community-based organizations. Findings reveal a predominance of top-down, event-driven messaging with limited feedback loops, while citizen-led initiatives remain largely confined to digitally connected, middle-income groups. Marginalized communities face exclusion from targeted communication, deepening health inequities. The study argues for more inclusive, bottom-up communication frameworks that recognize informal networks, aiming to strengthen transparency, participation, and resilience in Bengaluru's urban governance.

Keywords: Public health communication, urban governance, stakeholder mapping, dengue epidemic, Bengaluru

Introduction

Background

Bengaluru is widely recognized for its rapid urbanization and expanding population, conditions that have heightened the city's vulnerability to a host of governance challenges, particularly in the realms of climate adaptation, waste management, and public health (Menon & Hartz-Karp, 2019). Substantial gaps remain in how critical climate and health information flows between institutions, wards, and the citizens. Past studies have highlighted how the success of city-level interventions often hinges not only on identifying relevant stakeholders but also on understanding the channels and dynamics of communication among these actors (Biyani & Anantharaman, 2017; Ghosh, 2005).

Effective communication is vital for equitable access to information and services, especially for marginalized or vulnerable communities often left out of mainstream policy discourse (Sridhar & Smitha, 2021). However, entrenched social hierarchies, institutional fragmentation, and power differentials hinder the sharing of information and collaboration required for effective governance (Aivalli et al., 2025). Major knowledge gaps persist on how these barriers manifest in specific areas and what interventions could foster more inclusive, transparent communication and governance.

Rationale

Following the surge of over 25,000 dengue cases in 2024, Karnataka officially declared dengue as an epidemic disease (The Hindu, 2024). This notification coincided with the publication of the Karnataka Epidemic Diseases (Amendment) Regulations, 2024, amending the original Epidemic Diseases Act, 2020; the amended rules were published in the state gazette at the end of August 2024. Authorities will be able to levy penalties on households, commercial establishments, and construction sites for non-compliance under these new regulations (Bureau, 2024b).

Dengue cases saw a surge before the start of the monsoon season in 2025, with Bengaluru being the most affected city in Karnataka (Sri, 2025). In response to growing concerns about public health in the city, campaigns such as "Check, Clean, Cover" (Bureau, 2025b) and "Zero Dengue Starts with Me" (Raman, 2025) were launched until mid-2025, in addition to national-level nudges like the National Dengue Day (NCVBDC, 2017).

Along with awareness campaigns, the city government and municipal corporation have appointed several nodal officers (Bureau, 2024a) and brought together different departments (Bureau, 2025a; Desk, 2025) to work collaboratively to reduce dengue incidences.

This highlights the urgent need to prioritise urban health communication in Bengaluru from an accessible, ground-up, citizen-centric approach.

Objectives

Building on these observations, the research aims to:

- Map key stakeholders and analyze the flow of climate and public health communications across Bengaluru.
- Identify key barriers to information and participation, with a particular focus on marginalized and vulnerable groups.

By addressing these objectives, the study seeks to inform targeted communication interventions to enhance transparency, participation, and trust in Bengaluru's urban governance that can be scaled or adapted to similar urban contexts.

Methods

This research adopts a qualitative approach comprising of two main components:

1. Review of literature: The literature review was conducted using the PRISMA framework to identify relevant studies from peer-reviewed journals and newspapers.

- Databases searched: Okas Library via Zotero, Google Scholar, Google News
- Search period: 2020–2025
- Inclusion criteria: Peer-reviewed articles, government reports, NGO publications, and newspaper reports focusing on Bengaluru, climate, waste, public health, and urban governance.
- Review process:
 - Identification: Literature sourced using keywords like “Bengaluru”, “dengue control”, “flood management”, “waste management”, “heat stress”, “urban flooding”, “water-logging”, “advisory”, “guidelines”, “circular”.
 - Screening: Titles, abstracts, and full texts were reviewed for relevance.

2. Data collection and mapping

- Desk research: Synthesis of news reports, government advisories, and local organizing initiatives for climate and public health communication.
- Stakeholder identification: Mapping of stakeholders across Union government, State government, City government, Municipal Corporation/ urban local body (ULB) levels, such as resident welfare associations (RWAs), NGOs, CSOs, business groups, urban authorities, informal sector actors, and vulnerable communities.
- Communication pathways: Mapping of formal and informal channels, including digital media, print, radio, social networks, and word-of-mouth.

Risk of bias in the study

- Selection bias in literature: There is a risk that the literature included may not comprehensively reflect all relevant or granular perspectives. This can occur since the search is limited to English-language publications, potentially excluding literature or sources produced by grassroots organisations or local communities documenting experiences in the local Kannada language. As a result, certain stakeholder viewpoints or local insights may be overlooked, and the analysis would be based on dominant narratives.
- Reporting or publication bias: Studies with positive findings or large-scale interventions are more likely to be published and reported, while unsuccessful or neutral cases may remain underreported. This can lead to an exaggerated sense of the effectiveness of communication interventions in Bengaluru's governance landscape. Consequently, the review may underrepresent initiatives that failed or struggled to meet communities' needs.
- Researcher bias: Personal beliefs, disciplinary training, and prior experiences may unconsciously shape data selection, analysis, and interpretation.
- Data availability and accessibility: Communication pathways that rely on informal networks, such as word-of-mouth, community meetings, or closed messaging groups, are difficult to document as these may not appear in formal records or reporting found through a desktop search. This can lead to the underrepresentation of informal actors or mechanisms, particularly those predominant in lower-income or migrant communities. Furthermore, recent or unpublished developments might not be captured, limiting the study's timeliness and comprehensiveness.

Mitigation strategies for bias in the study

- Incorporating literature from local news sources and community-based organisations.
- Findings from literature and media are cross-validated to enhance reliability.
- Clearly outline limitations in data availability and acknowledge where specific perspectives may have been missed.

Results

The extended literature review (2020–2025) provides further insights into the nature of communication pathways for climate and public health issues in Bengaluru, with dengue serving as a primary case study.

Predominance of top-down communication

- Union, State, and City governments primarily disseminate advisories, SOPs, and updates through dashboards, mobile applications, and public campaigns (Bureau, 2023; Bureau, 2024a; Bureau, 2025b; Khanna, 2024; Service, 2024).
- These strategies tend to prioritize large-scale public messaging (e.g., “Check, Clean, Cover” and “Zero Dengue Starts with Me” campaigns) but rarely provide evidence of feedback loops that would allow citizen concerns to influence decision-making (Bureau, 2025a; Desk, 2025).

Citizen-led and intermediary communication

- Certain civil society organizations, particularly the Bengaluru Apartment Federation (BAF), have adapted government advisories for their communities, sharing them via YouTube and WhatsApp channels under the Kshema Health Wellness Programme (S, 2024).
- Platforms like the *I Am One Health* Festival facilitated dialogue among scientific, civic, and municipal actors, although tangible evidence of sustained community engagement beyond the event is limited (Pradhan et al., 2025).

Exclusion of marginalized voices

- A significant gap persists in documenting communication pathways targeting low-income groups, informal workers, or migrant communities. Neither government

advisories nor citizen-led initiatives reviewed make explicit reference to aligning communication for these populations.

- Reports highlight enforcement mechanisms (e.g., fines for mosquito breeding, crackdowns at construction sites) disproportionately affecting such groups, but without corresponding participatory channels for dialogue (Ramesh, 2025; P K, n.d.).

Emerging digital tools with limited uptake

- Innovations such as predictive models, dashboards, and AI-based apps (Bureau, 2023; Khanna, 2024) represent new tools for monitoring dengue and climate-health risks. However, critiques suggest these remain poorly integrated into local governance, with little clarity on accessibility for non-digital populations (Khanna, 2024).

Overall, results reaffirm a governance system characterized by high vertical communication, low horizontal collaboration, and limited bottom-up feedback.

Figure 1. Year-wise distribution of selected news reports

A year-wise distribution of the selected news reports (Figure 1) indicates a clear temporal trend in the communication of dengue-related public health issues in Bengaluru. Coverage remained relatively low in 2021–2022, with only five articles, before increasing modestly in 2023 (8 articles). A sharp spike occurred in 2024 with 25 reports, coinciding with the notification of dengue as an epidemic under the Karnataka Epidemic Diseases (Amendment) Regulations, 2024 (Bureau, 2024c) and intensified government action. In 2025, coverage appears to decline to 12 articles so far, suggesting a move from crisis-focused attention in 2024 to more routine reporting in the following year¹. These patterns point to the reactive

¹ While it is possible that the number of articles will increase as the year progresses, it is unlikely that they'll match up to the numbers from 2024 since Bengaluru actually experienced a 90% decline in dengue cases in July 2025, peak dengue season, compared to 2024 (Hindustan Times, 2025)

versus preventative and event-driven nature of communication and reporting on public health risks in the city.

Stakeholder mapping

Based on these news reports, a stakeholder map was developed to identify the key actors involved in climate and public health communication in Bengaluru and to trace the pathways through which information flows. The stakeholder map (Figure 2, Table 1) illustrates the diverse actors across four tiers of governance - Union, State, City, and Municipal Corporation/ULB - as well as civil society actors such as resident welfare associations (RWAs), NGOs, CSOs, and business groups. It also highlights their institutional levels, domains of influence, and interconnections. At the apex, Union government bodies such as the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW), National Health Mission (NHM), and India Meteorological Department (IMD) provide overarching policy frameworks, schemes, and programmatic guidelines. These are adapted by state-level entities like the Health and Family Welfare Department and the National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme (NVBDCP), which contextualize directives for implementation in Karnataka.

At the municipal and city governance level, the Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike (BBMP) and allied departments (solid waste management, stormwater drains, education, horticulture, etc.) act as primary operational agencies, supported by other city actors such as the Public Works Department (PWD), Urban Development Department (UDD), and Bengaluru Development Authority (BDA). The BBMP further delegates responsibilities to zonal officers, special commissioners, and nodal officers, ensuring coordination between infrastructure, health, water, and waste management functions. Block- and ward-level actors play a frontline role in community engagement, including District and Block Health Officers, ASHA and Anganwadi workers, Vector Borne Disease consultants, SHGs, PHCs, Namma Clinics, and Pourakarmikas. These stakeholders serve as critical links between higher-level policy and on-ground citizen engagement.

Citizens and community-based organizations (CBOs) such as Resident Welfare Associations, Bengaluru Apartments' Federation, Rotary Club, Lions Blood Bank, and student groups (NSS/NCC) contribute through awareness campaigns, voluntary action, and grassroots mobilization. Finally, research and knowledge institutions such as NIMHANS, IISc, ATREE, and ICAR provide scientific inputs, data, and technological innovations that strengthen evidence-based communication strategies.

By mapping these stakeholders, the diagram underscores the highly networked and multi-sectoral nature of public health communication in Bengaluru, where coordination between government agencies, frontline workers, community groups, and knowledge institutions is essential for effective disease prevention, awareness generation, and crisis response.

Disclaimer: This is not an exhaustive mapping of stakeholders involved in public health communication in Bengaluru, Karnataka

Figure 2. Stakeholder map for public health communication in Bengaluru, Karnataka

Discussion

The mapping highlights that while multiple government agencies disseminate information through formal channels (such as advisories, campaigns, and digital dashboards), civil society organizations and RWAs play a bridging role in contextualizing and relaying this information to specific communities. However, the influence of informal communication networks, such as word-of-mouth in lower-income settlements, remains under-documented, suggesting a blind spot in both research and policy attention.

The findings suggest that Bengaluru's climate–public health communication landscape remains fragmented and unevenly accessible. Top-down communication dominates, relying on digital and media channels that presuppose literacy, internet access, and institutional trust. While such strategies may help create widespread awareness, their effectiveness is compromised by the absence of citizen input and tailored approaches for vulnerable populations. This reactive pattern of communication highlights a key limitation in Bengaluru's governance landscape - information flow peaks during crises but is not sustained as part of long-term preparedness, thereby limiting opportunities for continuous citizen engagement and inclusive resilience building.

In contrast, citizen-led communication (e.g., RWAs, BAF) demonstrates the potential of community-level actors to contextualize and disseminate information. However, these efforts are largely restricted to middle- and upper-income groups with strong digital connectivity.

The absence of communication targeted at marginalized populations represents a critical governance gap (H. C. et al., 2024; Mandyam, 2024). Vulnerable groups face both a disproportionate disease burden and a lack of access to preventive information. This exclusion reflects broader inequities in urban governance where participation is shaped by socio-economic status, digital access, and institutional visibility. Finally, the adoption of digital tools without concurrent efforts at inclusivity risks reinforcing rather than bridging existing divides.

The stakeholder mapping exercise (Figure 2) reveals that communication flows in Bengaluru are heavily structured around top-down dissemination, with government agencies driving most campaigns and advisories. While RWAs and NGOs act as important intermediaries, especially in middle- and high-income neighbourhoods, the channels through which

vulnerable groups receive and engage with information remain unclear and underrepresented. This asymmetry points to a communication ecosystem that privileges formal institutions and digitally connected citizens, while informal actors and low-income communities are left at the margins.

The map also underscores the limited presence of feedback loops: although mechanisms such as toll-free numbers and WhatsApp helplines exist, their uptake and accessibility among diverse socio-economic groups appear weak. Although formal communication dominates, emerging evidence suggests informal networks play an essential but under-recognized role. Community leaders, shopkeepers, and anganwadi workers often serve as conduits for disseminating information, particularly in areas with low digital access. These findings suggest that strengthening bottom-up participation and recognizing informal networks as legitimate communication channels will be critical to building a more inclusive and equitable urban health communication system.

Table 1. Stakeholder and roles

#	Governance Tier	Example Actors	Communication Role
1	Union/State/City Govt	MoHFW, Health Department, BBMP	Formal advisories, apps
2	Municipal Corporation/ULB	Ward officials, health inspectors	Neighbourhood campaigns
3	Wards	Ward committees, area sabhas, RWAs, civic groups, NGOs, shopkeepers, migrant unions	Guideline adaptation, bridge to communities, word-of-mouth

Conclusion and Future Directions

The study so far reveals that effective governance in climate and health requires not just the dissemination of information but also inclusive, bidirectional communication frameworks. Bengaluru's current communication ecosystem risks privileging digitally connected, higher-income communities while neglecting those most exposed to health and climate vulnerabilities. Despite systemic gaps, the adaptation of government advisories by the Bengaluru Apartment Federation and participatory events like the One Health Festival

(Pradhan et al., 2025) show that locally contextualized, community-led initiatives can enrich civic engagement, albeit within privileged groups. Such models might be piloted in lower-income neighbourhoods with support from municipal authorities and local NGOs. Without deliberate efforts to bridge these gaps, communication interventions may remain symbolic rather than transformative.

To strengthen this research, future work should address existing data gaps by supplementing desk-based analysis with field-level interviews that capture informal communication practices such as word-of-mouth networks and community meetings, which remain largely undocumented. Incorporating Kannada-language sources and community media will also help move beyond an over-reliance on English-language narratives, ensuring that local voices and experiences are better represented. The thematic scope of the study should be expanded beyond dengue to include other climate-related hazards such as urban flooding and heat stress, in order to test whether similar patterns of exclusion and communication gaps persist across different risks.

Additionally, there is a need to systematically evaluate equity in communication by developing a framework that assesses who is reached by specific campaigns, disaggregated by income, gender, and digital access. Since direct documentation was unavailable, future interviews with frontline workers and local NGOs could clarify how public health messages are received and acted upon in low-income areas. Finally, exploring participatory models, such as those outlined in the Spectrum of Public Participation framework, can help identify feasible and inclusive interventions tailored for Bengaluru's governance landscape.

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